

MATERIAL PROPERTY STEERED OPTIMIZATION OF A MULTIFUNCTIONAL BODY PANEL TO STRUCTURAL AND ACOUSTIC CONSTRAINTS

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SUMMARY

A conventional automobile roof, including structural and interior trim components, is replaced with a multi-layer, multi-functional sandwich construction. A weight optimization is performed to tailor the material properties of the composite face sheets and multiple foam layers to meet structural constraints and acoustic requirements.

Keywords: Sandwich structures, multifunctional, optimization, automotive acoustics

INTRODUCTION

The vast majority of modern automobile structures are constructed by spot welding together pressed metallic components. Body panels, such as the roof, hood, trunk lid, etc, often have large areas of unsupported sheet metal which vibrate when subjected to external inputs such as aerodynamic loadings, or perturbations from the drivetrain or suspension system. The current state of the art relies heavily upon the use of viscoelastic damping treatments to control these vibratory phenomena [1], and prevent the formation of an unpleasant acoustic environment within the passenger compartment of the vehicle. While these treatments are capable of reducing noise and vibration levels, effective implementation often relies heavily on experimentation and the experience of the engineer [2, 3].

Reducing structural weight and increasing structural stiffness, specifically with respect to automotive body-in-white (BIW), often leads to increased problems with structurally borne sound and vibration within the vehicle. Here, sandwich structures offer the possibility of increased structural stiffness at a reduced mass, while at the same time eliminating some of the vibrational problems encountered with large sheet metal components. The load bearing capacity of

sandwich structures also presents the possibility of eliminating additional components necessary with a sheet metal design and thus offering greater weight savings potential.

An alternative approach to acoustic damping is the use of porous elastic media, such as light weight, open celled foams. By implementing multiple layers of foams, and varying their properties, favourable acoustic behaviour can be achieved at a relatively low weight penalty in contrast to viscoelastic damping treatments. More importantly, the treatments can be accurately tuned for a specific behavioural response using models based on numerical methods for poro-elastic media [4].

Within this paper, a multilayered, multifunctional sandwich panel concept has been proposed which includes the functionality of the following conventional components present in the roof of a passenger car: outer sheet metal, panel damping treatments, acoustic absorption treatments, structural reinforcement, and interior trim. The panel consists of composite face sheets, and multiple layers of structural and acoustic foam. This configuration has been suggested as a method of meeting the structural and quality needs present in an existing vehicle design.

The panel is mass optimized to a given set of structural and acoustic constraints using material properties of the various layers as design variables in addition to the layer thicknesses. Results of the two-part optimization are presented. Mass is compared with that of the conventional design, and results of static and dynamic load cases are examined.

In addition to the new panel having a reduced mass compared to the sum of the conventional components, a single modular concept containing multiple functionalities offers new possibilities in the assembly process. While reduced mass can result in a direct improvement in fuel economy, potential changes to the assembly line could improve assembly ergonomics and decrease assembly time. This twofold improvement in design benefits both the end user as well as the vehicle manufacturer.

METHOD

The work in this paper has been carried out in the following manner.

Firstly, a novel concept is proposed where multiple structural and acoustic components are replaced with a single multi-layered sandwich construction. The novel concept is mass optimized to a set of structural constraints. Static deflection and normal vibration behaviour are used as constraints. Mechanical properties and thicknesses of the various layers are used as design variables. In this stage, acoustic layers are kept constant and assumed to be linearly elastic. No acoustic effects are accounted for.

The mass optimized panel is then acoustically optimized. Here, thicknesses of the acoustic layers are altered as is the degree of perforation of the interior face sheet. Design variables used in the previous structural optimization are held constant.

The two step optimization process is repeated until a solution which satisfies both structural

and acoustical constraints is achieved with negligible change in parameters between the two optimization steps.

Both structural and acoustic optimization were performed using optimization tools based on the method of moving asymptotes (MMA) [5]

CONCEPT PROPOSAL

A conceptual design was proposed based upon geometry of a full size wagon-type passenger car. The panel was a four layer construction consisting of the following components:

- Outer face sheet – Glass fibre reinforced vinyl-ester composite laminate
- Structural foam layer – thermoplastic based expanded polymer foam (closed cell)
- Acoustic foam layer – multi-layer, low stiffness, open celled elastic foams
- Inner face sheet – CSM Glass fibre reinforced sheet, perforated for acoustic functionality

Figure 1: Cutaway view of panel concept

The exterior face sheet of the panel is an eight layer symmetric quadraxial glass fibre laminate. The acoustic foam layer is split into two pockets via a continuous layer of structural foam around perimeter of the panel as well as a transverse section at the panels midpoint. This is done to achieve structural integrity of the entire panel. The innermost face sheet is a CSM glass fibre reinforced plastic perforated with circular holes in a rectangular pattern to allow fluid interaction between the passenger cavity and the acoustic foam in the sandwich panel. Figure 1 shows a cutaway view of the proposed construction.

STRUCTURAL OPTIMIZATION

Structural modelling

Structural analysis was performed using the commercial software NXNastran 6.0. Structural and acoustic foam were modelled using multiple layers of CHEXA (3-D brick) elements and the perforated inner face sheet was modelled using a single layer of the same element type. Linear isotropic material properties (Nastran MAT1) were used. Due to their low stiffness, acoustic foam layers were modelled as a single material with density calculated based on the acoustic foam layer thicknesses. The outer face sheet was modelled using a combination of CQUAD and CTRIA (3-D shell) elements with composite laminate material properties (Nastran MAT8). For a more information on element or material property descriptions, please see the documentation for NXNastran [6].

Design variables and material properties

For the structural optimization, a total of nine design variables were chosen. These variables were as follows:

1. Volume fraction fibre (V_{f0}) in 0° layers of outer face sheet
2. Volume fraction fibre (V_{f45}) in $\pm 45^\circ$ layers of outer face sheet
3. Volume fraction fibre (V_{f90}) in 90° layers of outer face sheet
4. Lamina thickness, (t_0), of 0° layer of outer face sheet
5. Lamina thickness, (t_{45}), of $\pm 45^\circ$ layer of outer face sheet
6. Lamina thickness, (t_{90}), of 90° layer of outer face sheet
7. Thickness of structural foam layer
8. Thickness of inner face sheet
9. Density of structural foam layer

Fibre volume fraction for each of the lamina was allowed to vary from a minimum of 0.4 to 0.6, typical values seen for vacuum injection moulding. Fibre volume fraction was used to steer the mechanical properties of each lamina. Longitudinal Young's modulus, E_{11} , was determined according to the rule of mixtures, as shown in equation 1. Transverse Young's modulus, E_{12} , was calculated according to the serial model as shown in Equation 2, as it gives a lower bound for the possible modulus of the material. Equations 1 and 2 were taken from the literature [7]. Shear moduli for in-plane shear, G_{12} , G_{13} , and out-of-plane shear, G_{23} , were calculated using Equations 3 and 4. Poisson's ratio for the lamina, ν_{lamina} , was calculated according to equation 5. Equations 3 through 5 can also be found in the literature [8]. Equations 1 through 5 represent the full range of mechanical properties necessary to define the laminate in Nastran. Table 1 shows the material data used.

$$E_{11} = (V_f)E_{f11} + (1.0 - V_f)E_m \quad (1)$$

$$E_{12} = E_{13} = \frac{V_f}{E_f} + \frac{1 - V_f}{E_m} \quad (2)$$

$$G_{12} = G_{13} = \frac{G_m}{1 - \sqrt{V_f}(1 - G_m/G_{f12})} \quad (3)$$

$$G_{23} = \frac{G_m}{1 - V_f(1 - G_m/G_{f12})} \quad (4)$$

$$\nu_{lamina} = V_f \cdot \nu_f + (1 - V_f) \cdot \nu_m \quad (5)$$

Table 1: Material properties for matrix, fibres, and CSM sheet (non-perforated)

	Matrix	E-Glass	CSM Laminate
$E_{11}(tensile)$ [MPa]	3200	70000	15000
$G_{12} = G_{23}$ [MPa]	1185	30130	5769
ρ [kg/m ³]	1125	2580	1700
ν [-]	0.35	0.22	0.3

Assuming a closed-cell structural foam, the following relationship describes the variation of mechanical properties of a the foam based on its density and the mechanical properties of the raw material [9].

$$\frac{E_{foam}}{E_{solid}} \approx \phi^2 \left(\frac{\rho_{foam}}{\rho_{solid}} \right)^2 + (1 - \phi) \frac{\rho_{foam}}{\rho_{solid}} + \frac{P_0(1 - 2\nu_{foam})}{E_{solid} - \rho_{foam}/\rho_{solid}} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{G_{foam}}{E_{solid}} \approx \frac{3}{8} \left(\phi^2 \left(\frac{\rho_{foam}}{\rho_{solid}} \right)^2 + (1 - \phi) \frac{\rho_{foam}}{\rho_{solid}} \right) \quad (7)$$

$$\nu_{foam} \approx \frac{1}{3} \quad (8)$$

Recycleability was of interest and so a thermoplastic foam based on PET was proposed. Mechanical properties of four different foams available on the market were examined to correlate the manufacturers data with Equations 6 and 7, and to examine whether the assumption that $\phi = 0.8$ as given in the literature [9] is in fact valid. The four PET foams examined were DIAB Divinycell P series, and Airex T90, T91, and T92. Mechanical properties from technical data sheets available on the manufacturers homepage were used.¹

¹http://www.diabgroup.com/europe/products/e_divinycell_p.html
<http://www.corematerials.alcancomposites.com> Retrieved April, 2009

Plots of compressive Young's modulus and shear modulus for the different foams can be seen in Figure 2. Equations 6 and 7 are also plotted in Figure 2. It is interesting to note in the figure that two differing formulations of material seem to be used for low density and high density foam respectively. The low density foams (Divinycell P, Airex T92) have a larger stiffness increase for a given density than that of the high density foams (Airex T90, Airex T91). While it would be possible to fit Equations 6 and 7 well to the high or low density foams respectively, it was decided to use a curve more suitable to the entire range of foams. Here, a factor of $\phi = 0.7$ fit the manufacturers data reasonably well. A correction of 0.8 times Equation 7 was used to better match the data for shear modulus.

Figure 2: Mechanical properties of selected foams

Perforation geometry for the inner face sheet can be seen in Figure 3. Rather than modelling the individual holes, a method of modelling the perforated solid as a homogeneous material with perforation-equivalent properties was desired.

Figure 3: Perforation geometry of inner face sheet

For a panel perforated with circular holes in a rectangular pattern the relative density, ρ^* , based on the pre-drilled panel volume, can be calculated using the materials bulk density, ρ , and the hole pattern geometry. This is shown in Equation 9:

$$\rho^* = \rho \left(1 - \left[\frac{\pi}{4} \left(1 - \frac{S_x - d}{S_x} \right) \left(1 - \frac{S_y - d}{S_y} \right) \right] \right) \quad (9)$$

For a thin plate ($t \ll d$) with holes in a rectangular pattern ($S_x = S_y$) the literature [10, 11] provides a relationship between the bending stiffness of a perforated, D^* , and non-perforated, D , plate as follows:

$$\frac{D^*}{D} = \left\{ 1 - \frac{\pi}{4} \left(1 - \frac{S_x - d}{S_x} \right)^2 \right\}^{(2S_x - d)/0.8S_x} \quad (10)$$

Where D is simply:

$$D = \frac{E \cdot t^2}{12(1 - \nu^2)} \quad (11)$$

Assuming then that the effect of the change in Poisson's ration (ν) is negligible, the same relationship can be used to describe the relative Young's modulus E^* of the perforated plate based on hole geometry as shown in equation 12 :

$$E^* = E \left\{ 1 - \frac{\pi}{4} \left(1 - \frac{S_x - d}{S_x} \right)^2 \right\}^{(2S_x - d)/0.8S_x} \quad (12)$$

While perforations do in fact have a small influence on the Poisson's ratio as documented in [12], for this work, a simplification of assuming a constant value of $\nu = 0.3$ was used throughout.

For the structural optimization, a single degree of perforation was used and only thickness of the layer was altered.

Load cases and boundary conditions

For the structural optimization, two static and one dynamic case were analyzed.

The first static analysis included a localized load of 150 N applied to the roof spread over a circular area of approximately 100 mm in diameter.

The second static load case involved a uniform distributed pressure across the entire outer surface of the panel equivalent to 1.25 times the vehicles weight.

The dynamic analysis was a normal modes analysis to calculate the frequency of the first mode of vibration of the panel.

Boundary conditions for all the structural analysis were as follows; along the sides of the panel, all edge nodes in all layers were constrained in x, y, z directions. Along the front and rear edge of the panel, the lowermost edge of the bottom face sheet was constrained in x, y, z . This boundary condition was considered the most reasonable representation of in-service conditions possible.

ACOUSTIC OPTIMIZATION

Acoustic Modelling

For the acoustic calculations a structurally simplified model was used which excluded the framework of structural foam around the perimeter of the panel. Curvature of the panel was also ignored. Focus was instead placed on the large panel areas consisting of outer face sheet, structural foam, and acoustical trim components in the roof which consisted of three layers of porous foam and the perforated inner face sheet. An air cavity was connected to the roof panel to evaluate the sound pressure level (SPL) inside the vehicle compartment. To minimize calculation time, a 1/4 model of the entire panel was used with symmetry constraints. The perforated inner face sheet was, in the acoustical sense, regarded as an equivalent porous foam.

The acoustic response of the system was calculated using an FE-based numerical model [13, 14] where the porous layers were described using Biot theory [15, 16, 17]. In Biot theory a number of space averaged properties are used to model the dynamic and acoustic response of the foam structure and the moving fluid in the foam. The material properties of the acoustic foams used and the model to calculate equivalent space average properties for the perforated plate may be found in Appendix A.

Load cases and boundary conditions

The 1/4 model panel was excited using two phase-shifted dynamic forces at positions corresponding to where the a- and b-pillar (and due to symmetry also the c- and d-pillar) would introduce vibrations in the structure. As the acoustic panel only represents a part of the entire roof the layers were constrained in the x- and y-direction along the edges.

Acoustic design variables

For acoustic optimization, three design variables were chosen as follows:

- Thickness of the first acoustic foam layer $t_{ACFoam1}$.
- Thickness of the third acoustic foam layer $t_{ACFoam3}$.
- Degree of perforation of the interior face sheet.

Using the FE-based numerical model the A-weighted sound pressure level (SPL) in a sub volume of the air cavity was calculated for the frequency range 100-500 Hz with a 1 Hz frequency resolution. The sub volume was chosen to represent a possible listening position for a passenger. As with the structural optimization, the objective function for the acoustical optimization was the panel mass. Constraints were placed on the A-weighted SPL in the cavity and the optimization method MMA was utilized.

Table 2: Results of optimization

	Initial Sandwich	St. Iteration 1	Ac. Iteration 1	St. Iteration 2	Ac. Iteration 2
Mass (% of Conventional)	69.7	77.2	70.9	69.2	68.6
Static Disp. Load Case 1 (% of Max)	121.2	73.1	69.6	79.4	79.2
Static Disp. Load Case 2 (% of Max)	151.9	99.9	93.5	100.0	100.3
1st Mode Frequency (% of Min)	92.3	107.2	110.0	109.6	110.0
SPL deviation from Max [dB(A)]	-1.89	-3.70	-0.27	+0.43	0.00

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After two complete iterations all constraints were fulfilled, and changes to the panel between structural and acoustic optimization were negligible. Results of the optimization for each stage in process are shown in Table 2.

Firstly, it should be noticed that the initial configuration did not in fact, fulfil the structural requirements. Despite this fact, the method has been able to achieve a valid solution. The final configuration shows a significantly reduced mass compared to the conventional steel construction, and a slight reduction compared to the initial configuration. In addition, both the local static and global dynamic stiffness of the panel have improved in comparison with the conventional solution. The results of the optimization show that the limiting design constraint was the global panel stiffness for the distributed pressure load case.

Results for the design variables can be seen in Table 3. Volume fraction fibre for each layer reached the maximum value and remained there. The 45° layers were thickest, followed by the 0° layer which was approximately half as thick, and finally the 90° layer which was half as thick again. The results of the laminate alterations are interesting in that while the minimum thickness for the 90° layer were reached, the stiffness for that layer was still maximized despite the fact that a reduction in stiffness (via reduced V_{f90}) would lead to a slightly lower density, and thus a lower mass. This is likely due to the fact that a reduction in stiffness in the 90° layer would necessitate an increase in thickness (as increase in stiffness is not possible) for the other layers, which causes a larger increase.

Structural foam density and thickness essentially reached the minimum and maximum allowable values respectively. This is also somewhat predictable behaviour taking into account the sandwich effect; i.e. that for a sandwich panel with thin faces and a weak core, stiffness scales quadratically with core thickness whereas the effects of core stiffness are negligible. As the

Table 3: Results of optimization

Design Variable	Final Value
$V_{f0} / V_{f45} / V_{f90}$ [-]	0.6 / 0.6 / 0.6
$t_0 / t_{45} / t_{90}$ [mm]	0.224 / 0.521 / 0.125
t_{ACFoam} Layer1/2/3 [mm]	1.00 / 1.00 / 7.50
t_{STFoam} [mm]	19.868
ρ_{STFoam} [kg/m ³]	50.149
$t_{InnerFaceSheet}$ [mm]	0.693
$d/S_{x,y}$ (Perforation Dimensions) [mm]	2.0 / 2.5

total thickness of the sandwich was restricted and local deformations were part of the design constraints this result was not trivial from the outset.

An interesting difficulty arose when performing the acoustical optimization; the acoustic response function, used as a constraint, appeared to have a rather large number of local minima. This may be due to a number of reasons. One possible explanation is that small changes of the panel's effectiveness as an acoustic isolator at specific frequencies in the frequency interval may interfere with possible standing wave phenomena in the air cavity.

CONCLUSIONS

A novel, multi-layer, multifunctional sandwich panel capable of fulfilling the structural and acoustic functionalities of a conventional welded steel car roof has been proposed and weight optimized against a set of structural and acoustic constraints. A two step process of structural and acoustic optimization using mass as the objective function has been developed. A combination of commercially available and in house finite element analysis software has been used together with the method of moving asymptotes. Static and dynamic structural load cases as well as an acoustic load case have been used.

The resulting panel shows a significant reduction in mass compared to the conventional solution with no acoustic penalty. The optimization has shown that for the specific application, certain layers and materials within the construction have a more significant effect on its final configuration. Potential for further reductions in mass may exist by removing certain layers, or changing the materials within the layers.

With respect to the acoustic analysis, it is at this stage, too early to draw any conclusion of the origin of the local minima of the acoustic response function. The issue will, however, be addressed in future work.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work presented in this thesis has been carried out within the centre for ECO² Vehicle Design at the Department of Aeronautical and Vehicle Engineering, KTH.

Funding is provided via Vinnova, the Swedish Road Administration, the Swedish Rail Administration, the Swedish National Road and Transport Research Institute, KTH Aeronautical and Vehicle Engineering and KTH Environmental Strategies Research, and industrial partners: Scania CV, Bombardier Transportation, AB Volvo, Saab Automobile AB and A2Zound. The financial support of all parties is gratefully acknowledged.

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Appendix A: Biot Theory and Parameters

The space averaged properties for the perforated plate needed in the Biot theory were derived based upon the geometry of the plate and the assumption of flow in cylinder.

The porosity ϕ is the volume fraction of fluid in the structure and was defined as:

$$\phi = 1 - \frac{\rho^*}{\rho}$$

The flow resistivity of porous material is defined as the ratio between the pressure difference across a sample and the velocity of flow of air through that sample per unit cube. Here work by Allard and Champoux [18] were used to derive the static flow resistivity, σ^{static} :

$$\sigma^{static} = \frac{32\eta}{d^2\phi}$$

Where η is the viscosity of air, equal to $1.84 \cdot 10^{-5}$. The characteristic lengths is dependent of the ratio of the pore surface to the pore volume and are used to determine the energy losses due to heat transfer and viscous effects between the fluid and the solid parts in the porous material. For cylindrical pores the viscous characteristic length, Λ , is equal to the thermal characteristic length, Λ' . [19]:

$$\Lambda = \Lambda' = \frac{d}{2}$$

Tortuosity, α_∞ , is a parameter which is related to the complexity of apertures in the poro-elastic material. To be specific, it is determined in the ratio between the averaged length of the apertures in the poro-elastic material and the thickness of the material. As the inner structure becomes more complex and the tortuosity becomes higher. Due to the straight cylindrical shape of the holes in the perforated plate the tortuosity was set to unity.

For the porous foams the following properties were used

Table A-1 : Material properties for the acoustical foams

Material property	Foam 1	Foam 2	Foam 3
E [Pa]	$290 \cdot 10^3$	$1000 \cdot 10^3$	$50 \cdot 10^3$
ρ^* [kg/m ³]	50	250	30
ϕ [-]	0.91	0.3	0.94
Λ [m]	$60 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$80 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Λ' [m]	$120 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$4 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$160 \cdot 10^{-6}$
σ^{static} [N · m ⁻⁴ s]	$120 \cdot 10^3$	$5000 \cdot 10^3$	$67 \cdot 10^3$
α_∞ [-]	2.2	2.2	2.2